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Elemental Analysis of Opaque Thin Film Coating on Mobile Phone Scratch Cards

By

T. S. Bichi
P.O. Akusu
S.B. Muhammad

Research Article

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T. S. Bichi^{1*}, P. O. Akusu², S. B. Muhammad³ and Mallam, S. P

¹Department of Physics, Kano University of Science and Technology, Wudil

²Nigeria Atomic Energy Commission (NAEC), Abuja

³Ministry of Education, Kano State

^{1*}Corresponding Author's Email: tsbichiosh@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The opaque thin film material used to cover the Personal Identification Numbers (PIN) on mobile phone scratch cards for three GSM lines coded A, B and C is collected in three separate small plastic bottles. The substance is introduced to the nozzle of an XRF machine in order to determine its elemental composition. Results show that the substance used by all the three GSM lines to cover the PIN on their respective scratch cards mainly contains metals such as titanium, potassium, iron, calcium and zinc. It also shows complete absence of radioactive isotopes such as Uranium, Thorium, Radium or polonium in the substance. The implications of these findings are discussed in the paper.

Keywords: XRF Machine, Elemental Content, Telecommunication and Scratch Card.

INTRODUCTION

The last few decades witnessed great achievements in science and technology leading to inventions of various electronic devices, that in one way or the other have help to improve our attitude and the living standard of our lives. Telecommunication experts hatched these achievements into reality by producing mobile telephonic devices called handsets that are conveniently used by people to communicate with one another at places where telephone services are available. To add to the convenience, the experts in the marketing units of the GSM companies devised ways of enabling customers pre-pay for services provided by purchasing scratch cards for the respective GSM lines at their convenience. These cards carry Personal Identification Numbers (PIN) which are concealed under a thin coat of an opaque shiny substance. This paper deals with the elemental analysis of the opaque coating.

Handling the Opaque Substance

It has been observed that most people use their fingernails to scratch off the thin film opaque substance in order to reveal the PIN on the recharge cards for the recharging of their GSM lines. Mostly, these acts of scratching are done subconsciously or trivially without resorting to washing of hands with clean water and soap. The observation of this practice lead to some questions like: how safe is the practice? And how harmful is the substance? The justification of this research effort lies in the seeking for answers to these nagging questions.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Three small plastic bottles were used to collect the samples (opaque substance) from the scratch cards of three GSM companies and labeled A, B and C. An XRF machine was calibrated and set ready for use. Enough samples from bottle A was transferred into a small transparent nylon bag. The bag containing the sample was placed on the surface of a wooden workbench and the nozzle of the XRF machine was put on top of the sample. The machine was set on to diagnose the elemental composition of the sample and the results automatically appeared on the screen. Same procedure was repeated for the samples in bottles B and C. The data were transmitted to computer system for further analysis.

RESULTS

It was discovered that the results for samples A, B and C are very similar. It seems that the GSM companies make use of substance with same elemental composition on their respective scratch cards. Results as shown in Table 1.1 through Table 1.7 give names of the elements and the corresponding amounts of such elements expressed in parts per million (ppm). The elements with infinitesimal amounts in the substance are tagged as 'below limit of detection (<LOD):

Table 1.1: Amounts for phosphorus, sulphur, chlorine and potassium

Reading	Unit	P	P +/-	S	S +/-	Cl	Cl +/-	K	K +/-
1	PPm	2088	208	958	146	780	68	340	23

Table 1.2: Amounts for calcium, titanium, chromium and manganese

Ca	Ca +/-	Ti	Ti +/-	Cr	Cr +/-	Mn	Mn +/-
436	25	13634	96	19	3	81	3

Table 1.3: Amounts for iron, cobalt, nickel and copper

Fe	Fe +/-	Co	Co +/-	Ni	Ni +/-	Cu	Cu +/-
341	5	<LOD	19	<LOD	31	149	9

Table 1.4: Amounts for zinc, arsenic, selenium and rubidium

Zn	Zn +/-	As	As +/-	Se	Se +/-	Rb	Rb +/-
312	7	<LOD	3	<LOD	1.8	4.2	0.5

Table 1.5: Amounts for strontium, zirconium, molybdenum and silver

Sr	Sr +/-	Zr	Zr +/-	Mo	Mo +/-	Ag	Ag +/-
26.9	0.9	<LOD	2.5	<LOD	3.5	<LOD	11

Table 1.6: Amounts for cadmium, tin, antimony and iodine

Cd	Cd +/-	Sn	Sn +/-	Sb	Sb +/-	I	I +/-
<LOD	13	211	18	21	6	<LOD	112

Table 1.7: Amounts for barium, mercury and lead

Ba	Ba +/-	Hg	Hg +/-	Pb	Pb +/-
<LOD	61	<LOD	5.2	7.8	3.6

DISCUSSION

Tables 1.1 to 1.7 above show that the opaque thin film substance under investigation mainly contains metals such as titanium, iron, potassium, calcium, zinc and tin as well as some non-metal elements such as phosphorus and sulphur. It is also evident from the results that radioactive isotopes or radionuclei such as uranium, thorium, radium or polonium are completely absent from the substance. Thus the fear of inducement of cancer and related ailments that might arise due to careless handling of the substance is put to rest.

Figure 1.1: Bar Chart for the Elements and their Respective Concentration

Figure 1.1 above is the bar chart for the elements with their corresponding concentrations in parts per million. The bar chart shows that titanium is the most abundant element in the substance having a concentration of about 13,700 ppm. The next abundant element found in the substance is phosphorus whose concentration is about 2,200 ppm which is less than one-sixth of the concentration of titanium while sulphur has a concentration of about 1,100 ppm which is less than one-twelfth of titanium.

It has been revealed that high concentration for tin, titanium and phosphorus in the substance are however the source for concern. Ingestion of 200mg/kg of tin can lead to nausea, vomiting and diarrhea (Blunden *et al.*, 2003). Organotin compounds can be very toxic such as tri-n-alkyl tins which are phytotoxic. Care should therefore be taken to make sure that intake of tin element does not reach beyond 50mg/kg tin (Food Standard Agency, 2002).

Similarly, higher concentration of phosphorus in the substance may be disturbing. White phosphorus is toxic and it causes severe liver damage when ingested in high concentration (Macleod and Rogers, 2007). It also causes a disease called phossy jaw commonly suffered by occupational workers in match industries (Lisandro, 2005). It is quite relieving that use of white phosphorus is prohibited (ATSDR, 2005). However, the presence of titanium in the substance may be of less concern since titanium powder used as shaving powder are not toxic to the skin. Titanium may however react with chlorine in the air to form titanium chloride which is very corrosive in nature.

Elemental sulphur does not pose much danger to man or his environment. But sulphuric substances such as hydrogen sulphide, sulphur dioxide or sulphurous acids may have effects on human health. Few of such effects include heart damage, damage of liver and kidney functions, reproductive failure and eyesight effect (Lenntech, 2012). The concentration of potassium in the opaque thin films on GSM recharge cards is relatively insignificant. In fact, potassium in our metabolic system helps to balance high sodium intake in hypertensive patients and reduce the risk of high blood pressure (Darling, 1982).

It should be noted that Lead is present in the substance and despite its low concentration it may have a toxic effect when ingested frequently, with children being at higher risks (Fertmann *et al.*, 2004).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained in the research it is concluded that the opaque thin film on GSM recharge cards does not contain radioactive isotopes/radionuclides that can lead to inducement of cancer and related ailments. The substance however, contains some transition metals and some non-metal elements which may be toxic if ingested at higher concentration.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i) Using fingernails to scratch off the substance is not a safe practice. Blunt razor blade or pair of scissors should be used instead.
- ii) Care should be taken not to contaminate our foods and drinks with the substance to avoid ingestion of the substance.
- iii) Warning statements concerning this opaque thin film coat should be clearly written on every recharge card by all service providers.

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